

JUST
WIND
4 ALL

EXPERT WORKSHOP

UAB
Universitat Autònoma
de Barcelona

Funded by
the European Union

Grant Agreement 101083936

Renewables
Grid Initiative

JUSTWIND4CATALUNYA

WORKSHOP – BARRIERS OF WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA AND THE ENBIOS SOCIO-ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT

Date: **March 29, 2023**

Location: [Institut de Ciència i Tecnologia Ambientals \(ICTA - UAB\) Room 023/022](#)

The European-funded research project, JustWind4All, is set to accelerate on- and offshore wind energy in sustainable and just ways, by tackling key challenges identified by the project's consortium: Knowledge gaps, Justice deficit, Unsuitable policy frameworks, and Unlocking novel resources.

We aim to tackle these challenges and advance just, sustainable wind by incorporating multiple approaches. From a socio-environmental perspective, the ENBIOS tool, developed by Institute of Environmental Science and Technology at the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (ICTA-UAB), aims to promote holistic energy impact assessment for fit-for-purpose decision-making. The ENBIOS tool has been used to assess impacts of the energy transition in Portugal and the European Union, as well as some of the scenarios proposed by the Integrated national energy and climate plan (PNIEC) of the government of Spain. In JustWind4All we will update ENBIOS to assess scenarios of wind energy implementation in Catalunya, Bulgaria and North Holland.

Catalunya is one of the main case studies in JustWind4All, with a key objective of adapting the ENBIOS tool to regional on- and offshore wind energy realities. Practical knowledge from diverse stakeholders in Catalunya and the South-West European region will be applied to improve the metrics of the ENBIOS tool, making it a more effective tool for energy transition planning and implementation.

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AGENDA

9:30 - 10:00	Registration and coffee
10:00 – 10:20	<p>Welcome and Intro to JustWind4All project & Workshop Objectives <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB) and Andrzej Ceglarz (RGI)</i></p> <p>Introduction to Catalunya's regional wind energy <i>Francesc Xavier Rehues Estivill (Department of Territory - Catalunya)</i></p>
10:20 – 11:20	<p>Interactive Expert Session 1: Identifying Barriers of wind energy in Catalunya World Café considering barriers of onshore and offshore wind energy <i>Andrzej Ceglarz and Amanda Schibline (RGI) to moderate</i></p>
11:20 - 11:35	Coffee Break
11:35 – 12:30	<p>Interactive Expert Session 2: Classifying & Prioritising the co-created Barriers Plenary exercise <i>Cristina Pérez Sánchez (UAB) to moderate</i></p>
12:30 – 13:15	<p>Interactive Expert Session 3: Information Gaps on Barriers Plenary exercise <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB) to moderate</i></p> <p>Key Takeaways from afternoon sessions <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB) and Andrzej Ceglarz (RGI)</i></p>
13:15 – 14:15	Lunch Break
14:15 – 14:45	<p>Introduction to Energy System Models and the Catalunya Energy Plan (PROENCAT) <i>Francesc Vidal (ICAEN)</i></p> <p>Introduction to the ENBIOS holistic impact assessment How ENBIOS has helped policymakers and visual aspects of ENBIOS <i>Cristina Madrid López and Miquel Sierra Montoya(UAB)</i></p>
14:45 – 15:20	<p>Interactive Expert Discussion: Energy Transition Barriers & Modelling Opportunities <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB)</i></p>
15:20 – 15:30	<p>Key Takeaways of Workshop and Next Steps <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB)</i></p>

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GETTING TO THE UAB CAMPUS

NEARBY PARKING LOTS FOR THOSE WHO ARRIVE BY CAR

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GETTING TO THE UAB CAMPUS

ICTA BUILDING MAP

Once inside the building, room 022/23 (where the workshop will be held) is close to the entrance, at the left.

WHO IS JUSTWIND4ALL?

**Funded by
the European Union**

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